

Supporting Information for:

Influence of Electronic Spin and Spin-Orbit Coupling on Decoherence in Mononuclear Transition Metal Complexes

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Experimental Section

General Considerations. Compounds were synthesized as previously reported unless otherwise specified. All compounds were analyzed for purity due to the sensitive nature of relaxation measurements. Results of the analyses are included below. Due to their reported photosensitivity, **1**,¹ **3**,² **4**,³ and **5**⁴ were synthesized, manipulated and stored away from direct sources of light. $\text{K}_4[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]$ was synthesized as previously reported,⁵ and $\text{K}_4[\text{Os}(\text{CN})_6]$ was synthesized as reported below. All other precursors were purchased from commercial vendors.

$\text{K}_4[\text{Os}(\text{CN})_6]$ was synthesized via a modified literature method,⁵⁻⁷ with $\text{OsCl}_3 \cdot 3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (0.750 mg, 2.14 mmol) replacing OsO_4 as a reagent. The reaction was heated at reflux for 11 hours at which point the reaction began to form a white precipitate. The crude, light peach-colored reaction mixture was cooled and filtered to remove the white precipitate, then purified by repeated precipitation and washing with water/methanol solutions as described for $\text{K}_4[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]$. The compound was then used without further purification. IR spectra matched well with those previously reported.⁸⁻¹¹

$\text{K}_3[\text{Ru}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 4.5(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**1**•**4.5**(H_2O)) was synthesized using 'Method B' from a previously-published procedure with $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.509 g, 5.643 mmol, $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3.33\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from the certificate of analysis) as the starting material.¹² The recrystallization from water reported in the literature procedure was modified as follows. The crude product was dissolved in 40 mL of water and the solution was evaporated to a volume of ~2 mL, resulting only in the growth of blade-shaped potassium hydrogen oxalate (KHC_2O_4) crystals¹³ which were a translucent grey-brown color by transmitted light. A gentle flow of air was then maintained over the final 2 mL of mother liquor, resulting in the crystallization of a mass of prismatic chunks that were green by reflected light and amber by transmitted light. This mixture was filtered and the crystals were rinsed with 4×1.5 mL of cold water, then allowed to dry in air. A powder X-ray diffraction pattern of the crushed crystals confirmed bulk purity of the product,¹⁴ a tan-yellow powder (0.2464 g, 7.7%). The IR spectrum matched well with previously reported values.¹⁵ Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{K}_3\text{O}_{16.5}\text{Ru}$: C, 12.79; H, 1.61%. Found: C, 13.08; H, 1.24%.

$\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 0.5(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**2**•**0.5**(H_2O)). The trihydrate was synthesized according to literature methods.¹⁶ Magnetic measurements were taken on the trihydrate. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot 3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{CrK}_3\text{O}_{15}$: C, 14.79; H, 1.24%. Found: C, 14.39; H, 1.08%.

EPR and IR data were collected on a sample which was dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 200 °C overnight. The IR spectrum matched well with previously reported values.¹⁵ Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{HCrK}_3\text{O}_{12.5}$: C, 16.29; H, 0.23%. Found: C, 16.20; H, < 0.5%.

$\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**3**•**3**(H_2O)) was purchased from Alfa Aesar and used without further purification. The IR spectrum matched well with previously reported values.¹⁵ Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{FeK}_3\text{O}_{15}$: C, 14.67; H, 1.23%. Found: C, 14.74; H, 0.97%.

The sample used for magnetic measurements was dried *in vacuo* for 24 hours at 100 °C over P₂O₅. Anal. Calcd. for K₃[Fe(C₂O₄)₃]•0.7(H₂O) (C₆H_{1.4}FeK₃O_{12.7}): C, 16.02; H, 0.31%. Found: C, 16.05; H, < 0.5%.

(Ph₄P)₃[Fe(CN)₆]•3(H₂O) (4•3(H₂O)) was synthesized by precipitation from a concentrated solution of the potassium salt, as previously reported.¹⁷ A solution of K₃[Fe(CN)₆] (300 mg, 0.911 mmol) in water (1.5 mL) was added to a 45 °C stirring solution of (Ph₄P)Br (1.142 g, 2.724 mmol) in water (35.0 mL), and the solution was filtered hot. Yellow needles formed in the filtrate upon cooling and were isolated by filtration, then rinsed with 3 × 1.5 mL cold H₂O and allowed to dry in air (861 mg, 73.6%). The CN stretching frequency matched that previously reported.¹⁸ IR (cm⁻¹, diamond ATR): 3503 (w, br), 3080 (w), 3057 (w), 2098 (s), 1651 (m), 1618 (w), 1584 (m), 1482 (m), 1437 (s), 1342 (w), 1317 (m), 1191 (w), 1168 (w), 1106 (vs), 1073 (w, sh) 1030 (w), 996 (s), 933 (w), 853 (w), 758 (s), 720 (vs), 689 (vs), 616 (w), 524 (vs), 456 (w). Anal. Calcd. for C₇₈H₆₆FeN₆O₃P₃: C, 72.95; H, 5.18; N, 6.54%. Found: C, 73.31; H, 4.91; N, 6.65%.

(Ph₄P)₃[Ru(CN)₆]•0.5(CHCl₃) (5•0.5(CHCl₃)) was synthesized via modification of the previously published procedure.^{4,19} Our approach exploited the product's increased stability in organic solvents.²⁰ K₄[Ru(CN)₆] (300 mg, 0.725 mmol) was dissolved in 28.0 mL of water, then 28.0 mL of MeOH was added slowly with vigorous stirring. A suspension of Ce(SO₄)₂•xH₂O (306 mg, 0.725 mmol, Ce(SO₄)₂•5H₂O, from the certificate of analysis) in 3.0 mL water was then added to the clear solution, and the suspension was stirred vigorously for 5 minutes. Subsequently, the suspension was immediately filtered, yielding a yellow filtrate and sea foam-colored solids. A solution of (Ph₄P)Br (456 mg, 1.09 mmol) in 3.0 mL MeOH was added to the filtrate, followed by extraction with 4 × 9.0 mL CH₂Cl₂. The yellow-orange organic layer was collected and dried over MgSO₄, then evaporated to dryness. (It is essential that the filtration, addition of (Ph₄P)Br, and extraction be performed in rapid succession as the product degrades over the course of ~1 hour in 50/50 H₂O/MeOH solution.)

The product was crystallized first by slow evaporation of 20 mL of a 1:1 solution of CH₂Cl₂/CHCl₃ to remove excess (Ph₄P)Br, and then recrystallized by diffusion of pentane vapor into 6 mL of a 5:1 solution of CH₂Cl₂/CH₃Cl, yielding orange-yellow crystals of **5•2(CHCl₃)•2(CH₂Cl₂)** suitable for X-ray diffraction (162.3 mg, 26.6% with respect to (Ph₄P)Br). IR (cm⁻¹, diamond ATR): 3058 (m,br), 2935 (m, br), 2089 (s), 1585 (m), 1483 (m), 1436 (s), 1338 (w, sh), 1316 (m), 1257 (w), 1188 (w), 1164 (w), 1105 (vs), 1028 (w), 996 (s), 748 (s), 719 (vs), 686 (vs), 659 (s), 616 (w), 523 (vs), 454 (w), 437 (w).

The product was then dried *in vacuo* for 24 hours. Anal. Calcd. for (Ph₄P)₃[Ru(CN)₆]•0.5(CHCl₃) (C_{78.5}H_{60.5}Cl_{1.5}N₆P₃Ru): C, 70.62; H, 4.57; N, 6.30%. Found: C, 70.49; H, 4.95; N, 6.33%.

(Ph₄P)₃[Os(CN)₆]•2(H₂O) (6•2(H₂O)) was synthesized via the previously reported procedure.⁶ Anal. Calcd. for C₇₈H₆₄N₆O₂OsP₃: C, 66.89; H, 4.61; N, 6.00%. Found: C, 66.49; H, 4.31; N, 6.04%. The IR spectrum matched that previously reported.

Magnetic Measurements. Magnetic measurements were performed on polycrystalline samples sealed in a polyethylene or polypropylene bag. All data were collected using a Quantum Design MPMS-XL SQUID magnetometer from 1.8 to 300 K at applied dc fields ranging from 0 to 7 T. Dc susceptibility data were corrected for the core diamagnetism of each sample using Pascal's constants.²¹

EPR Measurements. Pulsed EPR data were obtained at the National High Magnetic Field Laboratory (NHMFL) at X-band frequency (9.734–9.737 GHz) on a Bruker E680 spectrometer equipped with an ER 4118X-MD5 dielectric resonator, which was overcoupled to a Q of about 150. All pulsed measurements were collected on 1.0 mM frozen solutions in 1:1 (v/v) H₂O/glycerol (~10 μL in a 3mm OD quartz tube). Temperature was controlled with an Oxford Instruments CF935 helium flow cryostat and an Oxford Instruments ITC503 temperature controller. The temperature controller was calibrated with a 100 Ω Allen-Bradley resistor submerged in mineral oil in a 4 mm OD quartz EPR tube, which was in turn calibrated by immersion in liquid helium, liquid nitrogen, and room-temperature air.²² Helium pressure in the cryostat was maintained between 800 and 900 mbar to ensure good thermal contact between the gas and the sample.

Prior to acquiring T_2 measurements, the field of maximum echo intensity was determined by incrementing the applied dc field and applying a standard two-pulse Hahn echo sequence [$\frac{\pi}{2} - \tau - \pi - \tau - \text{echo}$] at each field. The resulting echo-detected field-swept (EDFS) spectra and experimental parameters used for their collection are shown in Fig. S2. T_2 relaxation times were then measured at the field corresponding to the maximum echo intensity using a standard two-pulse Hahn echo sequence, in which the $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and π pulses used were 40 ns and 80 ns, respectively. The pulse lengths were chosen to minimize electron spin echo envelope modulation (ESEEM), which can complicate fitting of the decay curve, while still maintaining sufficient signal intensity to allow data collection. Pulse power was adjusted by attenuation of the pulse amplifier to maximize echo intensity, and an initial delay (d1) of 300 ns was inserted directly after the $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and π pulses in all T_2 experiments to eliminate resonator ringdown and other effects. Unwanted artifacts were suppressed via 2-step phase cycling. The number of data points collected varied between measurements within the range 350–800 points; the specific number of points for each measurement was chosen such that at least half of the spectrum consisted of baseline, in order to obtain good fits to the data. Between 3 and 80 scans were averaged for each decay curve, and either 30 or 100 shots per data point were taken, both depending on the signal intensity. Other experimental parameters for all T_2 measurements: 69 dB video gain, 20 MHz video bandwidth, 999.6 μs shot repetition time, 12 ns τ increment size.

Echo decay curves were phased by minimization of the standard deviation of the imaginary component of the data, and the real component of the data was then fitted to a stretched exponential function $I(2\tau) = I(0)\exp(-(2\tau/T_2)^x)$ using a Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (where 2τ is twice the interpulse delay time and x is the stretch factor). For each measurement the entire decay curve was fit, despite the occasional occurrence of artifacts in the first $\sim 1 \mu\text{s}$ of the imaginary component of the data, to ensure consistency between all fits. Data exhibiting significant modulation (**2**, **4**, **5** and **6** at low temperatures) were still fit to the unmodulated stretched exponential function as fits to a modulated stretched exponential function produced similar values of T_2 . The standard deviation from the fit of each T_2 and x value is reported in parentheses following the value.

Transient nutation experiments on **1** were performed at 4.7 K under a 2812 G static field using a three pulse sequence [$t_p - T - \frac{\pi}{2} - \tau - \pi - \tau - \text{echo}$] where T and τ were held constant (typically 18000 ns and ~ 900 ns, respectively) and t_p was incremented in 4 ns steps starting with an initial value of 0 ns. Measurements were acquired at four different pulsed field (B_1) strengths, and the $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and π pulse lengths were optimized to give the maximum echo intensity at $t_p = 0$ for each value of B_1 . Values of the video gain, video bandwidth, and shot repetition time were the same as for T_2 measurements. Between 30 and 60 scans were averaged for each measurement, and 30 shots were taken per data point. The oscillations were phased by minimization of the standard deviation of the imaginary component of the data, and the Rabi frequency was determined by zero-filling the resulting Rabi oscillation curves (originally containing 300 data points) out to 1024 points and performing a fast Fourier transform on the resulting data set.

High-field continuous-wave EPR (CW-EPR) spectra on saturated solution samples were collected at the NHMFL, using a transmission probe in which microwaves are propagated through cylindrical lightpipes. High-frequency microwaves were generated by a phase-locked Virginia Diodes solid-state source operating at 13 ± 1 GHz, followed by a chain of multipliers and amplifiers. Microwave detection was provided by a bolometer. High magnetic fields were provided by a 17 T superconducting magnet.²³ Spectra for **1–3** are depicted below; spectra for **4–6** were found to be consistent with previously published spectra (refs. 24, 20, and 6, respectively).

X-ray Structure Determination. Single crystals suitable for X-ray analysis were coated with Paratone N oil and mounted on a MiTeGen MicroLoop™. The crystallographic data were collected at 100 K on a Bruker KAPPA APEX II diffractometer equipped with a MoK α sealed tube diffraction source with a graphite monochromator, and a Bruker APEX II detector. Raw data were integrated and corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects with SAINT v8.27B.²⁵ Absorption corrections were applied using SADABS.²⁶ Space group assignments were determined by examination of systematic absences, E-statistics, and successive refinement of the structures. Structures were solved using direct methods in SHELXS and further refined with

SHELXL-2013²⁷ operated with the OLEX2 interface.²⁸ Crystallographic data and the details of data collection are listed in Tables S7 and S8.

In the crystal structure of **4**, seven solvent water molecules were successfully assigned. Hydrogen atoms on two of the water molecules were refined freely, however the hydrogen atoms on the remaining water molecules were not assigned, as their electron density could not be conclusively located in the difference map. All other hydrogen atoms were fixed at calculated positions using suitable riding models and refined using isotropic displacement parameters derived from their parent atoms. Three of the oxygen atoms in the solvent water molecules were modeled as disordered over two sites, and one oxygen atom was modeled as disordered over three sites. Thermal parameters were refined anisotropically for all non-hydrogen atoms, with the exception of three of the disordered oxygen atoms, which were refined isotropically.

In the structure of **5**, three CHCl_3 molecules, two CH_2Cl_2 molecules, and one site that was occupationally disordered between CHCl_3 and CH_2Cl_2 were assigned. In the disordered site, one of the constituent chlorine atoms of the dichloromethane was further positionally disordered between two locations. The interatomic distances between chlorine atoms in the occupationally disordered chloroform molecule were restrained to be equal, as were the Cl–C bonds in that molecule. The Cl–Cl distances in all dichloromethane molecules were restrained to be equal. All hydrogen atoms were placed at calculated positions using suitable riding models and refined using isotropic displacement parameters. Thermal parameters were refined anisotropically for all non-hydrogen atoms, with the exception of four disordered solvent chlorine atoms.

Other Physical Measurements. Elemental analyses for **5** and $\mathbf{2}\cdot\mathbf{3}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ were performed by Midwest Microlabs LLC (Indianapolis, IN), and those for the remaining compounds were performed by Galbraith Laboratories (Knoxville, TN). Infrared spectra were recorded on a Bruker Alpha FTIR spectrometer equipped with an attenuated total reflectance accessory.

Figure S1 | Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility data for **1–6**. These plots demonstrate the variation in the properties of each series. The increasing spin from **1** to **3** manifests in increasing $\chi_M T$ values. The increasing spin orbit coupling of **4–6** is demonstrated by the decreasing curvature of the plot across this species, which indicates better isolation of the ground spin-orbit coupled levels in **6** relative to **4**. Data sets were collected on polycrystalline samples sealed in polyethylene or polypropylene bags under dc fields of $H_{dc} = 0.5$ T (**2**) and $H_{dc} = 1$ T (**1**, **3–6**). Collected data compare favorably with literature precedent (refs. 29, 30, 31, 32, 4, and 6 for **1–6**, respectively.)

Figure S2 | Echo-detected field-swept (EDFS) EPR spectra of **1–6**. Experimental parameters for collection of all spectra: 40 ns $\pi/2$ pulse length; 30 shots per point; 2-step phase cycling; 999.60 μ s shot repetition time; 69 dB video gain; 20 MHz video bandwidth; 4.6–4.9 K collection temperature. Parameters which varied between spectra: 300 ns initial delay (d1) for **1–3** and **5**, 600 ns for **4** and **6**; 7.0 dB pulse power attenuation for **1**, 12.5 dB for **2**, 14.6 dB for **3**, 4.0 dB for **4**, 4.7 dB for **5**, 5.5 dB for **6**; 8 averaged scans for **1**, 33 scans for **2**, 4 scans for **3**, 16 scans for **4**, 10 scans for **5**, and 22 scans for **6**. High-quality spectra were only collected in the field range where there was significant echo intensity, as determined by an initial EDFS spectrum recorded from 500 to 9500 G.

Table S1 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **1** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 2812 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 7.0 dB.

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.7	3.44(1)	1.82(2)
8.4	3.37(1)	1.85(1)
13.7	2.01(1)	1.34(1)
17.2	0.89(1)	0.98(1)
21.8	0.41(2)	0.84(3)

Figure S3 | T_2 decay curves for **1** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **1** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 2812 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 7.0 dB.

Table S2 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **2** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 2130 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 12.5 dB.

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.7	2.79(3)	1.54(3)
8.1	2.50(3)	1.45(4)
13.5	1.86(3)	1.18(3)
17.1	1.68(3)	1.16(3)
21.2	1.27(4)	0.98(4)

Figure S4 | T_2 decay curves for **2** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **2** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 2130 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 12.5 dB.

Table S3 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **3** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 3501 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 14.6 dB. Data are in good agreement with previously reported T_2 values.³³

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.6	1.83(1)	1.09(1)
8.2	1.30(1)	0.99(1)
13.5	0.81(1)	0.96(1)
17.3	0.56(3)	0.91(5)
21.5	0.45(5)	0.88(9)

Figure S5 | T_2 decay curves for **3** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **3** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 3501 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 14.6 dB. Data are in good agreement with previously reported T_2 values.³³

Table S4 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **4** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 3364 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 4.0 dB.

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.7	2.38(6)	1.26(5)
8.4	1.80(3)	1.25(4)
12.5	0.55(8)	0.70(8)
17.6	0.55(6)	0.64(6)
21.6	0.60(9)	0.77(10)

Figure S6 | T_2 decay curves for **4** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 3364 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 4.0 dB.

Table S5 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **5** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 3394 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 4.7 dB.

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.7	2.55(4)	1.06(2)
6.1	2.55(4)	1.05(2)
13.2	1.25(5)	0.91(4)
17.6	1.06(7)	0.75(4)
21.4	1.29(10)	0.82(6)

Figure S7 | T_2 decay curves for **5** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **5** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 3394 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 4.7 dB.

Table S6 | T_2 values and stretch factors, symbolized as x , for 1.0 mM frozen solutions of **6** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol collected under a static field of 3865 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 6.0 dB.

Temperature (K)	T_2 (μ s)	x
4.6	4.12(6)	2.39(11)
8.6	4.06(4)	2.53(9)
13.5	3.17(4)	2.19(9)
17.3	1.88(4)	1.88(10)
21.7	1.04(4)	2.4(3)

Figure S8 | T_2 decay curves for **6** at variable temperatures. Solid lines represent a fit of the data to a stretched exponential function. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **6** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 3865 G with a pulse power attenuation setting of 6.0 dB.

Figure S9 | Rabi oscillations for **1** at 4.7 K. Data were collected on a 1.0 mM frozen solution of **1** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol under a static field of 2812 G. Here, B_1 values are expressed relative to the value of B_1 at 16.0 dB attenuation from full power (e.g. relative $B_1 = \sqrt{10^{-0.1A}/10^{-1.6}}$ where A is the attenuation in dB).

Figure S10 | CW-EPR spectrum of **1**. Data were collected at 10 K on a concentrated frozen solution of **1** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol with a microwave frequency of 208.0 GHz. The asterisk denotes a $g = 2$ impurity, and the low field signal denoted by ♦ is due to oxygen.

Figure S11 | Variable-frequency CW-EPR spectra of **2** (left), and comparison with simulations (right). Data were collected at 10 K on a concentrated frozen solution of **2** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol. The vertical offsets of the spectra at left are proportional to the microwave frequency. Fitting the z and xy components of the spectra yielded parameter values of $g_x = g_y = 1.975$, $g_z = 1.990$, and $D = -0.71 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (see Fig. S12). The sign of D was obtained by comparison of simulated spectra with the experimental spectrum (right). These parameter values are a good match to those previously reported for **2** in various solid dilutions, except that the sign of D found here is the opposite of that previously found by magnetometry.^{34,35}

Figure S12 | Fits to variable-frequency CW-EPR spectra of **2**. Plots depict the dependence of the field on the microwave frequency of the z-component (left) and xy-component (right) of each transition. The slopes of the lines formed by each set of points allow for accurate determination of g , D and E (see Fig. S11).

Figure S13 | Variable-frequency CW-EPR spectra of **3**. Data were collected at 10 K on a concentrated frozen solution of **3** in 1:1 H₂O/glycerol at 208.0 GHz (left) and 324.0 GHz (right). The asterisk denotes a $g = 2$ impurity. Inset graphs depict a magnified downfield portion of the spectra, showing a weak feature at ~ 3.5 T (left) and ~ 5.5 T (right). The experimental data were compared to simulated spectra which were constructed using the previously-reported parameters of $g = 2.00$, $D = 0.18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $E = 0.055 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and were found to be a good match.³⁶ In these spectra, the strong, higher-field transition corresponds to a combination of the five allowed ($\Delta M_S = 1$) transitions, while the signal at lower field corresponds to a combination of the four formally forbidden $\Delta M_S = 2$ transitions.

Figure S14 | Thermal ellipsoid plots of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ in **4** (left), and $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ in **5** (right), drawn at the 30% probability level. Cations and solvent molecules have been omitted for clarity. Orange, light blue, gray, and dark blue ellipsoids correspond to Fe, Ru, C, and N atoms, respectively.

Table S7 | Crystallographic information for the structural refinement of $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]\cdot 7(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**4**•7(H₂O)).

Empirical Formula	$\text{C}_{78}\text{H}_{74}\text{FeN}_6\text{O}_7\text{P}_3$
Formula weight	1356.22 g mol ⁻¹
Temperature	100 K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal System	Triclinic
Space Group	<i>P</i> -1
Unit Cell Dimensions	$a = 12.5029(4)$ Å, $\alpha = 76.828(2)^\circ$ $b = 15.7866(5)$ Å, $\beta = 84.688(2)^\circ$ $c = 18.7568(6)$ Å, $\gamma = 73.539(2)^\circ$
Volume	3455.5(2) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	2
Density (calculated)	1.303 g cm ⁻³
Absorption coefficient	0.347 mm ⁻¹
F_{000}	1402.0
Crystal color	Yellow
Crystal size	0.24 × 0.18 × 0.13 mm ³
θ range	1.115 to 28.796°
Index ranges	-16 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 16 -21 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 21 -25 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 25
Reflections collected	106543
Independent reflections	17899 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0764$]
Completeness to $\theta = 28.796^\circ$	99.3%
Absorption correction	Multi-scan
Maximum and minimum transmission	0.746 and 0.694
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data / restraints / parameters	17899 / 1 / 888
Goodness-of-fit on F^{2a}	1.020
Final <i>R</i> indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] ^b	$R_1 = 4.79\%$, $wR_2 = 11.07\%$
<i>R</i> indices [all data]	$R_1 = 6.56\%$, $wR_2 = 12.05\%$
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.73 and -0.68 e Å ⁻³

^a GooF = $[\sum[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (n-p)]^{1/2}$ where n is the number of reflections and p is the total

number of parameters refined. ^b $R_1 = \sum||F_o| - |F_c|| / \sum|F_o|$; $wR_2 = [\sum[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum[w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}$

Table S8 | Crystallographic information for the structural refinement of $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})_3[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3.3(\text{CHCl}_3) \cdot 2.7(\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2)$ (**5**·3.3(CHCl₃)·2.7(CH₂Cl₂)).

Empirical Formula	$\text{C}_{84}\text{H}_{68.7}\text{Cl}_{15.3}\text{N}_6\text{P}_3\text{Ru}$
Formula weight	1899.29 g mol ⁻¹
Temperature	100 K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal System	Monoclinic
Space Group	<i>Cc</i>
Unit Cell Dimensions	$a = 24.7221(9)$ Å $b = 15.0978(6)$ Å, $\beta = 114.4650(10)^\circ$ $c = 25.3767(13)$ Å
Volume	8621.4(6) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	4
Density (calculated)	1.463 g cm ⁻³
Absorption coefficient	0.760 mm ⁻¹
F_{000}	3850.0
Crystal color	Orange
Crystal size	0.25 × 0.25 × 0.13 mm ³
θ range	1.763 to 27.147°
Index ranges	$-31 \leq h \leq 31$ $-19 \leq k \leq 19$ $-32 \leq l \leq 32$
Reflections collected	70928
Independent reflections	18493 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0683$]
Completeness to $\theta = 27.147^\circ$	99.7%
Absorption correction	Multi-scan
Maximum and minimum transmission	0.746 and 0.670
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data / restraints / parameters	18493 / 14 / 998
Goodness-of-fit on F^{2a}	1.027
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] ^b	$R_1 = 4.03\%$, $wR_2 = 9.47\%$
R indices [all data]	$R_1 = 4.60\%$, $wR_2 = 9.85\%$
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.88 and -0.94 e Å ⁻³
Flack parameter	$-0.009(10)$

^a GooF = $[\sum[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (n-p)]^{1/2}$ where n is the number of reflections and p is the total

number of parameters refined. ^b $R_1 = \sum||F_o| - |F_c|| / \sum|F_o|$; $wR_2 = [\sum[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum[w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}$

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